

Skills 4 eosc

Pilot course for RI professional (MS 5.1)

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Deliverable Abstract

The data management course is designed to help RI managers enhance their skills and knowledge in defining and implementing key data management policies across the research lifecycle. Key topics include creating comprehensive data policies, establishing and respecting FAIR principles for data, and developing effective data management plans.

The document outlines the structure and the learning objectives of the pilot course, which was initially developed in the context of the RltrainPlus project and further updated in alignment with the Skills4EOSC objectives and outputs.

The course is divided into four sessions:

- Introduction to data management and data policy for RI managers
- Operational oversight of data management and policy in an RI
- FAIR principles and their application
- Data management plans

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
CPD	Continuing Professional Development
CF	Core Facilities
ESMRI	European School for Management of Research Infrastructures
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure

TtT

Train-the-Trainer

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1 Executive summary

The Data Management pilot course for RI professionals was developed as part of Task T5.1 of the Skills4EOSC project, which aims to design modules on Open Science (OS) and FAIR Research Data Management (RDM) specifically tailored for Research Infrastructure (RI) professionals. The primary objective of the course was to establish a framework for implementing best practices in data management and data policy within RIs. It served as a preparatory step for the Skills4EOSC Train-the-Trainer (TtT) course, aimed at upskilling Competence Centre experts and research professionals.

The modules were created in collaboration with the RItrainPlus project, which focuses on establishing the European School for Management of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI). This collaboration was made possible through the task leader, who also coordinates the RItrainPlus project.

The pilot course was developed in September 2024 and it was attended by 30 participants.

It was designed as a Continuing Professional Development (CPD) course at post-EQF 8 level, with the general aim of developing Competence (Knowledge, Skills, Attitude and Behavior) for professionals already employed in RIs and Core Facilities (CFs).

The learning model, teaching tools, and methodologies included online modules, lectures, group work, case discussions, role plays, sharing best practices, and assignments. Faculty members from the RI contributed to module design and provided problems, case studies, and scenarios for developing rich active learning materials. The delivery of the pilot course was followed by a thorough assessment and fine-tuning of the learning modules.

The learning objectives of the course are to:

- i) Understand the key issues and concepts around the management of data and data policy within an operational RI.
- ii) Situate the RI within a typology of research infrastructures and appreciate how this influences the treatment of data management and policy.
- iii) Assess the different factors at play when implementing data management and policy in real-time settings, such as resources, technologies, and staff competencies.
- iv) Apply the methodologies of the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) and FAIR-by-Design developed within the Skills4EOSC project to ensure that training modules are tailored to the specific needs of RI professionals.

2 Course on data management for RI professionals

Data are at the core of most research infrastructures and core facilities, managers and operators of research infrastructures need skills in how to handle data management and in how to set and execute data policy. The course is aimed at managers, operators and other professionals in Research Infrastructures or Core Facilities and provided a comprehensive overview of the key issues and concepts around the management of data and data policy in Research Infrastructures. It covered topics such as the role of data policy, data typologies, metadata, operational considerations for managers, data lifecycle, workflows, user groups, open data, data sharing and access restrictions, certification mechanisms, and FAIR principles. After completing the course, participants are able to develop relevant data management policies and guidelines, determine resources, technologies, and staff competencies needed to implement data management and policy, and implement FAIR principles in their research infrastructure.

The pilot was delivered in September 2024, with an aim to serve as a framework for a comprehensive learning path on FAIR and RDM for RI professionals. 30 participants were professionals working in research infrastructures or core facilities.

The teaching methods consisted of online lectures and exercises, homework assignments after each module. Slides were used as the main support for in-class instruction. For many of the exercises there were “break-out rooms” in smaller groups. Also, collaborative tools were used to dynamize the lessons such as Mentimeter and Google Jamboard.

Feedback and assessment were conducted through a designed survey. Participants were invited to complete a questionnaire, and all data were collected in full compliance with EU GDPR regulations.

2.1 Learning Objectives

Group of Learning Objective	Learning Objective
Data management policies	Identify and develop relevant data management policies for research infrastructures, throughout the data lifecycle
Data management policies	Define appropriate workflows, roles, and responsibilities among RI staff for data management
Data management policies	Understand, catalogue and manage different types of data (understood in a broad sense: datasets, software, workflows, etc.) that are handled and generated in the RI and by RI users

Data management policies	Setup the data management plan policies and ensure that RI staff and researchers develop data management plans according to these policies
FAIR principles	Identify the FAIR principles that are applicable for the data generated by the Research Infrastructure
Security and privacy	Learn about the importance of data security and how to spot potential gaps within the infrastructure and internal processes.
Security and privacy	Learn about the importance of data privacy/protection policies and techniques and how to apply them
Preservation	Learn what is needed to make data and metadata accessible for the long-term (preservation)
Quality assurance	Best practices in quality assurance for data
Security and privacy	Data sharing and access (open data vs closed data) and restrictions/control, in an Open Science context
FAIR principles	How to manage metadata within your RI system (F of FAIR plus other elements of FAIR)
FAIR principles	Make the data of the RI more interoperable (I of FAIR)
FAIR principles	Make your data more findable and citeable (F of FAIR)
FAIR principles	Ensure that data can be used and reused as much as possible (R or F of FAIR)
Data management policies	Learn the certification mechanisms that are available for data management in different RIs/scientific communities, and be able to determine whether these are needed for your RI
Data management plans	Understand the importance of dedicated data management plans for increased data quality of the Research Infrastructures main assets.
Data management plans	Support compliance with Research Infrastructure's data management policies.
Data management plans	Contribute to knowledge exchange with regard to data management by Research Infrastructure's gateway function.
Data management plans	Focus on the essential cornerstones of research data management plans for increased quality of service provisioning.
Data management plans	Understand, catalogue and manage different types of data (understood in a broad sense: datasets, software, workflows, etc.).
Data management plans	Templating mechanisms for Data Management Plans.
Data management plans	Understand the different requirements for data and metadata descriptions related to different data types of various Research Infrastructures.
Data management plans	Develop an individual and personalised template for a data management plan for the research infrastructure.
Data management plans	Ensure improved quality of the draft template by expert level feedback after assessment of the provided data management plan template.
Skills4EOSC methodologies	Apply the methodologies of the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) and FAIR-by-Design developed within the Skills4EOSC project to

	ensure that training modules are tailored to the specific needs of RI professionals.
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The following paragraphs outline the details of the learning objectives.

2.1.1 Introduction to data management and data policy for RI managers

The introduction provides a framework for the course and presents the key concepts relevant to managing data and data policy within RIs, including definitions of data and typologies of RIs, the role of metadata, and operational considerations for managers.

After completing this Session, the participant will be able to:

- understand the key issues and concepts around the management of data and data policy within an operational RI;
- situate his or her own RI within a typology of research infrastructures, and appreciate how this influences the treatment of data management and policy;
- determine how different drivers affect how data management and data policy are implemented in an RI;
- assess the different relevant factors in play when implementing data management and policy in real-time settings, such as resources, technologies, and staff competencies.

2.1.2 Data Policy in Research Infrastructure Systems

This module covers the role of data policy and data management in RIs, including how data policy for different data management domains should be crafted and formulated for different audiences and purposes, and aligned with internal and external drivers and implemented in RI workflows. It also addresses how policy can be converted into practical guidelines for different user groups.

After completing this Session, the participant will be able to:

- identify and develop relevant data management policies for research infrastructure throughout the data lifecycle;
- define appropriate workflows, roles, and responsibilities among research infrastructure staff for data management and policy implementation;
- understand, catalogue, and manage different types of data (datasets, software, workflows, etc.) handled and generated in the research infrastructure and by its users;
- decide what is needed to make data and metadata accessible for long-term preservation;
- understand data sharing and access (open data vs closed data) and restrictions/control in an Open Science context; and
- assess certification mechanisms available for data management in different research infrastructures/scientific communities and determine whether they are needed for the research infrastructure.

2.1.3 FAIR principles and their application

This module focuses on deepening the participants' understanding of the FAIR principles and empowering them to adapt and extend the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability in their RI. By the end of this Session, participants will be able to set up the guidelines for FAIRness in their Research Infrastructure, and plan the development and/or integration of the protocols, techniques and tools required to achieve such FAIRness.

After completing this Session, the participants will be able to:

- understand the FAIR principles in general and the main concepts and vocabulary used;
- make data findable, understanding the most common metadata schemas and the importance of generating persistent identifiers;
- make data accessible, describing the different protocols to access data, both for humans and for machines;
- make data interoperable, using ontologies and other semantic artifacts;
- make data reusable, selecting the appropriate license and providing rich metadata to facilitate its reuse and provenance;
- implement FAIR principles in the setting of a real research infrastructure.

2.1.4 Data management plan for Research Infrastructures

Developing a reliable and specific data management plan is a core business of each research infrastructure. A data management plan ensures that the RI's data will be adequately described and made available to a broader public. This enables a more thorough perspective for the re-use of data and the formulation of innovative data-centric research questions. This Session turns the theoretical knowledge of data management policies and plans into practice.

After completing this Session, the participant will be able to:

- understand the importance of dedicated data management plans for increased data quality of the research infrastructures' main assets;
- support compliance with the research Infrastructure's data management policies;
- contribute to knowledge exchange with regard to data management by the research infrastructure's gateway function;
- increase the quality of service in their RI by improving the essential cornerstones of research data management plans;
- develop an individual and personalised template for a data management plan for the participants' research infrastructure;
- ensure improved quality of the draft template by expert-level feedback after assessment of the provided data management plan template.

3 Conclusions

The pilot Data Management course for RI professionals has provided valuable insights and allowed for a fine-tuning the Train-the-Trainer (TtT) course to upskill Master Trainers identified by the Competence Centres of the Skills4EOSC Network, as well as RI experts aiming to enhance their expertise in applying Open Science methodologies to research infrastructure management and research data management (RDM).

The finalized course will be delivered through the Skills4EOSC Learning Platform, ensuring broad accessibility and scalability. Its materials and methodologies, including the Minimum Viable Skillset and FAIR-by-Design approaches, will also be integrated into future courses provided by the European School for Management of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI). Furthermore, they will contribute to institutional initiatives such as InfraUNIMIB at UNIMIB and the Research Infrastructure Network at UiB, fostering a robust and sustainable culture of Open Science.